

NWO and ZonMw Open Access Monitor 2022

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Executive summary

This report analyses the openness of publications from research funded by NWO and ZonMw in 2022. The research was based exclusively on openly accessible metadata. Overall, 93% of the articles that were detected have been made available open access using one of the available open access routes (NWO: 93,1%; ZonMw: 92,7%). This is an increase compared to 2021 (90%) and 2020 (85%). At least 64% of the included NWO and ZonMw publications of 2022 (3.688 out of 5.763) has been published via Gold, Hybrid, under a transformative agreement, or Green OA, with a CC-BY license and is therefore fully Plan S compliant. Being Plan S compliant is mandatory for NWO and ZonMw research granted from 2021 onwards; many of the current publications analysed, are likely from grants from before 2021.

It is recommended that the future strategy of NWO and ZonMw should focus not just on reaching the 100% open access, but also on the costs, monitoring, development and quality aspects of open access in general.

1 Introduction

NWO implemented its initial open access (OA) policy in 2009, which emphasized the importance of making NWO-funded publications openly accessible "as soon as possible." In 2015, NWO turned its OA-policy into a formal mandate, in alignment with the Dutch OA ambitions presented by state secretary Sander Dekker back in 2013. The mandate stipulated that all publications supported by NWO must be openly accessible upon publication, preferably through the Gold OA route¹, while also acknowledging support for the Green OA route. For ZonMw OA is part of its grant requirements since 2013, requiring researchers to make all publications that emerge from research that is partially or entirely funded by ZonMw OA available "as quickly as possible".

In 2018 NWO joined cOAlition S and ZonMw followed in 2019. cOAlition S is an international group of funding councils that developed Plan S, a strategy to accelerate the transition to full and immediate OA for all (peer reviewed) publications that are the result of research funded by the participating funders. The requirements of Plan S apply to publications resulting from calls published by NWO and ZonMw from 1 January 2021 onwards. In practice, this means that compared to previous years the OA requirements have been tightened. For example, an embargo period isn't allowed anymore and publications should be published under a Creative Commons (CC BY or, by exception, CC BY ND) licence.

This OA monitor 2022 report, builds on three earlier CWTS-reports, covering publications from periods 2015–2018², 2015-2020³ and 2015-2021⁴. For those reports NWO requested CWTS to analyse the extent to which research funded by NWO is made openly accessible. The analyses in all three reports also covered publications funded by ZonMw.

Main conclusions of the last report (period of analyses 2015-2021, published in 2022) were:

1. At least 9 out of 10 publications in 2021 resulting from research funded by NWO and ZonMw are available OA. For NWO, this meant an increase of 5% compared to 2020, from 85% to 90%. For ZonMw-funded research, the increase is 9%, from 82% to 91%.
2. The number of publications in hybrid journals increased considerably in recent years, due to the OA deals universities have negotiated with publishers. The share of publications in full-gold journals also increased dramatically.
3. The monitor determined for the first time the share of diamond OA papers. An equitable model as neither authors nor readers face any costs. The international interest in this model has increased significantly in recent years, and has gathered even more traction since [the EU council conclusions of the 23rd of May 2023](#), where the Council calls for "transparent, equitable open access to scholarly publications".
4. Between scientific domains, there are no major differences in the overall OA score. The same is true for universities.

¹ For used definitions on OA-types see page 8.

² Waltman, L. (2020). Monitoring open access publishing of NWO funded research (final). [Zenodo](#).

³ Waltman, L. (2021). Monitoring open access publishing of NWO funded research (final). [Zenodo](#).

⁴ Waltman, L/ & Lamers, W.S. (2022). Monitoring open access publishing of NWO-funded research (2015-2021) (Version 1). [Zenodo](#).

1.1 OA monitor 2022

While the previously mentioned reports covered a longer timeframe, this report focuses only on the publication year 2022. Another difference is that the aforementioned previous reports were based on closed, proprietary databases, respectively Web of Science for the 2020 and 2021 reports, and Dimensions for the 2022 report. For this report, we are utilising exclusively openly available (meta)data for the first time. The decision to do so for this current OA monitor was driven by two primary reasons.

Firstly, this approach aligns with the principles of open science, embracing open and interoperable metadata and infrastructure as integral components. Secondly, the shift away from relying on commercial data sources was driven by the desire to avoid steep usage fees often associated with such services and sources. Additionally, these commercial databases tend to lack inclusivity, particularly in terms of coverage of disciplines. And last but not least this data from commercial parties cannot be shared openly and therefore validated and verified by others, which goes against the open science principles.

This new approach is in line with NWO and ZonMw's strong commitment to open science: the ambition should not only be to ensure that the outputs of NWO/ZonMw funded research are made available as immediately and openly as possible. NWO/ZonMw should also apply open science principles to their own procedures, by making data about funded research as open as possible and using open (meta)data for policy analysis, where possible. This new approach has the obvious drawback that a direct comparison with figures of previous reports cannot be made.

2 Methodology

The sources from which data were aggregated and used for this report are discussed first (Section 2.1), followed by the approach taken to identify publications funded by NWO or ZonMw (Section 2.2) and how the OA status of these publications was determined (Section 2.3). Finally, we discuss how we established a first overview of Plan S compliance (Section 2.4).

2.1 Data sources

The data and figures in this report rely on information gathered from open (meta)data sources and services, more specifically Crossref - the international non-for-profit membership organisation responsible for issuing DOI's for published academic works, the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), and Unpaywall. Data extraction from Crossref took place on the 27th of May, 2023 and information from Unpaywall and DOAJ was used to assess the openness status. Any necessary data cleaning, deduplication, validation and checking was conducted between June and August.

2.2 Identifying publications funded by NWO or ZonMw

To identify publications from NWO and ZonMw we used data from Crossref. As of 2013 Crossref allows publishers to deposit funding information metadata when registering publications DOI. To that end Crossref has developed the Funder Registry, an open registry of grant-giving organisation names and identifiers. This metadata can be accessed by using the Crossref REST API.

Funder acknowledgements

In both the NWO (Paragraph 4.1.3) and ZonMw (Article 17.4) grant requirements it is stated that for any publication the funder and the project-number needs to be acknowledged. Furthermore, authors should acknowledge financial and practical support in their published research articles. Authors typically do this by mentioning the funding agency and ideally grant number, usually in the acknowledgment section. Publishers play a crucial role by including funding acknowledgments and unique funder IDs in their standard article metadata.

- For this analysis publications were selected that could be identified by the funder ID for both NWO ([10.13039/501100003246](https://doi.org/10.13039/501100003246)) and ZonMw ([10.13039/501100001826](https://doi.org/10.13039/501100001826)).

In addition we selected (and deduplicated) records in which NWO or ZonMw were identified by their respective acronym:

- Query link: [NWO](#)
- Query link: [ZonMw](#)

We also included publications by researchers affiliated with NWO institutes. We determined the year in which a publication was published by the year in which the Crossref record for the publication was created, in this case the reporting year 2022. In exceptional cases, the journal issue in which a publication was published had an official publication date that preceeded the year in which the publication's Crossref record was created. In these instances, we used the year in which the journal issue was published as the year in which the publication was published.

Limitations

We need to acknowledge a few limitations with this approach. Since we have decided to rely entirely on funder acknowledgements and funding metadata from Crossref, we will have missed publications, which do not have this information. Some authors may have failed to acknowledge funding from NWO or ZonMw in their publications, or funding metadata could have been missing from the database as a result of being lost at another point in the publication process. The estimate is, and this has also been the assumption in the previous reports, that due to this missing information in articles we miss about 40-45% of the actual output coming from NWO or ZonMw-funded research⁵. In our opinion this should not be a reason to give preference to the use of proprietary (potentially more complete) bibliographic databases. The quality and completeness of open metadata on the global scholarly record will only improve if organisations like NWO and ZonMw start using it.

Books, book chapters and publications in conference proceedings are not included at all in this analysis.

Despite these limitations, the OA statistics in this report offer a reasonably complete overview of the extent to which publications funded by NWO or ZonMw have been made openly accessible and how that is being done.

Mitigating actions

NWO recently addressed the importance of complete and high quality open funder metadata by co-hosting [a round table](#) with Crossref, publishers and data experts. The call to all parties is to take funding metadata seriously and make every effort to include it in databases as completely as possible. NWO, and likely ZonMw, will do its part by [registering grant metadata](#) with Crossref. This means that each awarded grant will be assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier – a grant DOI – accompanied by standardised metadata that is available via APIs and can be programmatically exchanged with other platforms.

Another step that could lead to better visibility of funding information and uptake of funder acknowledgements is the NWOpen-API, which was launched early September 2023. The API makes NWO-funded research more findable, but NWO also sees it as a first step to facilitate the registration of research results by researchers. Researchers often find themselves needing to register information in multiple locations: at NWO, as well as at their own institute. In time, the NWOpen-API can hopefully contribute to linking systems and exchanging data back and forth with institutions and publishers.

2.3 Determining the open access status of publications

The OA-status of publications was determined by linking the publication database derived from Crossref to the Unpaywall database. For each publication funded by NWO or ZonMw, the Unpaywall database was used to determine whether the publication is OA or not, and its OA-type. An additional source of data is the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), which was used to distinguish between full OA journals that do or do not charge the author for publishing (by asking an Article Processing Charge – APC).

⁵ This is an estimate based on the results from the previous three reports (coverage WoS and Dimensions, and percentage having a funder acknowledgement) and a study that looked at registered publications in NWO registration system ISAAC with a funder acknowledgement: Kramer, B. & De Jonge, H. (2022) The availability and completeness of open funder metadata: [Case study for publications funded by the Dutch Research Council](#).

Five types of OA are distinguished⁶:

- Diamond OA. Publications in a full OA journal that charges no fees to both readers and authors.
- Gold OA. Publications in a full OA journal that does charge fees or for which the existence of fees is undetermined.
- Hybrid OA. OA publications in a subscription journal with a clearly identifiable licence.
- Bronze OA. OA publications in a subscription journal without a clearly identifiable licence.
- Green OA. Publications in a journal that are also available in an OA repository (e.g., in an institutional repository or on a preprint server).

Diamond OA journals were identified using data made available by DOAJ (qualification 'DOAJ – diamond'), with the condition that a journal requires neither an APC nor any additional fees for publishing.

Diamond, Gold, Hybrid, and Bronze OA are mutually exclusive. Green OA may overlap with the other types of OA. For instance, if a publication in an OA journal is also available in an OA repository, the publication is both Diamond or Gold OA and Green OA. In this report, we have chosen to classify a publication as Green OA only if it is not Diamond, Gold, Hybrid, or Bronze OA. In this way, each OA-publication is classified as exactly one of the five types of OA listed above.

Bronze OA publications lack an identifiable open licence. Their inclusion in the OA-statistics presented in this report can be debated. We manually examined a random sample of Bronze OA publications funded by NWO (N=10 out of 99) and ZonMw (N=5 out of 23). A majority of these publications in this sample seemed to be genuine OA publications. Based on this finding, and also because the subset is rather small (N=122), we decided to include bronze OA publications in the OA-statistics in this report.

Only publications made available through legal forms of OA publishing are considered in this report. Publications made available on Academic Social Network (ASN) platforms such as ResearchGate and Academia.edu or websites such as Sci-Hub or personal websites are not considered to be openly accessible.

Limitations

Two limitations must be recognised concerning the OA status of publications. Firstly, there might have been inaccuracies in the data from the Unpaywall database. Secondly, in our analyses of Green OA publications, for a small amount (N=29) the Unpaywall data lacks clarity regarding when these publications became openly accessible. Consequently, for those publications we cannot ascertain whether they were made openly available immediately upon journal publication or at a later date.

2.4 Establishing an overview of Plan S compliance

With the available data, we were able to assess the Plan S compliance of the included articles at a generic level. It should be noted that we looked at an overall picture of the use of licences as well as the use of embargoes. We did not specifically look at articles from grants that have to comply with Plan S conditions, as these conditions only became mandatory for calls published since 2021 onwards. In the current available funder acknowledgements/information it is not (yet) possible to automatically check whether an article falls within this updated policy change. In the coming years, we hope to be able to automate this process (see section 3.5).

⁶ We have used the same definitions as in the last CWTS report: Waltman, L/ & Lamers. W.S. (2022).

3 Findings

3.1 Open access status of NWO and ZonMw funded publications from 2022

We were able to detect a total of 5.763 publications for NWO and ZonMw. Of these, a total of 403 (7%) publications were closed. The OA-status of 5 publications could not be ascertained by Unpaywall. After manual checking, all 5 publications were available OA (1 Hybrid OA, 1 Green OA, 3 Gold OA) and have therefore been counted as such in the total figures (table 1). All other publications (5,360 publications) were detected and available open access. The table below shows a breakdown by the different OA types divided by organisation as well as totals.

NWO			ZonMw			Total		
OA type	# of publications	%	OA type	# of publications	%	OA type	# of publications	%
Closed	304	6,89%	Closed	99	7,31%	Closed	403	6,99%
Bronze	99	2,25%	Bronze	23	1,70%	Bronze	122	2,12%
Hybrid	1778	40,33%	Hybrid	489	36,12%	Hybrid	2267	39,34%
Green	1101	24,97%	Green	157	11,60%	Green	1258	21,83%
Gold	1093	24,79%	Gold	584	43,13%	Gold	1677	29,10%
Diamond	34	0,77%	Diamond	2	0,15%	Diamond	36	0,62%
Total # of articles	4409	100%	Total # of articles	1354	100%	Total # of articles	5763	100%

The following graphs give a visual representation of the distribution based on the outcomes by Unpaywall.

Figure 1. Total number of NWO publications (4409) divided by OA type.

Figure 2. Total number of ZonMw publications (1354) divided by OA type.

93% of the articles that were detected have been made available OA using one of the available routes (NWO: 93,1%; ZonMw: 92,7%). Publications from NWO are more depending on the Hybrid OA and the Green OA route, when comparing with ZonMw output. This can only partly be explained by the ZonMw approach, where since 2021 for many grants researchers could reserve a dedicated budget (EUR 5000) for APCs before the start of their research, under the conditions that the money could only be claimed if the article was published via Gold OA, and followed all Plan S conditions. This might have stimulated more researchers to choose Gold OA instead of Green OA. For NWO OA costs can be claimed within the annual material budget of EUR 15k per FTE within grants, but other costs are eligible as well, which means that in practice the material budget is only partially used for OA publishing.

Another explanation is that NWO and ZonMw research concerns different domains, and each domain might have other developments and preferences for routes, like in the life sciences where there is potentially more money for publishing available and are more fully OA publishers to choose from.

3.2 Licences and versions of open access publications

Diamond, Gold and Hybrid OA publications are published under specific licences. Figure 3 presents a breakdown by licence for NWO funded publications and Figure 4 presents a breakdown by licence for ZonMw funded publications.

Figure 3. A breakdown by licence for NWO funded publications.

Figure 4. A breakdown by licence for ZonMw funded publications.

Of the included publications, 64% have a CC-BY licence, the most liberal of the CC licences and fully Plan S compliant. The remaining publications almost all have a CC-BY-NC or CC-BY-NC-ND licence (13%). Less than 1% of publications have a CC-BY-SA or CC-BY-NC-SA licence or a publisher-specific licence (categorised under 'other'). We couldn't determine the licence of 16% of the publications (922 in total). Almost 7% of the publications gave back a 'licence n.a.' through Unpaywall, which means Unpaywall had no information about the licence type.

The CC-BY-NC and CC-BY-NC-ND licences are not compliant with Plan S. Publishers with the highest percentage of publications with these two licences (390 articles in total) include Taylor & Francis (26,9%), Elsevier (22,5%), Wiley (10%), Oxford University Press (8,9%), Royal Society of Chemistry (8,7%) and American Chemical Society (6,9%). Given that agreements exist with all of these publishers, there is still room for improvement in negotiating compliant licence arrangements in (new) transformative agreements.

3.3 Top 20 publishers and open access types

We also looked at the top 20 publishers where the articles were published and how the OA types are distributed for those publishers. Still, the dependency on Hybrid OA and Green OA can be seen at the majority of traditional publishers. Gold OA is still a minority for those publishers. We can also see that the full OA publishers Frontiers and MDPI are gaining a significant OA-market share (position #8 and #9).

Figure 5. The top 20 publishers for NWO and ZonMw publications in 2022, with the distribution of OA types.

3.4 Embargo periods

For those articles that have been made available by means of the Green OA route (depositing in a trusted repository) we have established the delay (in number of months) after which papers were made available. Many publishers enforce embargo periods of up to 12 or 24 months and sometimes longer, when the Green OA route is applied. In the case of the Green OA route, Plan S requires the accepted version ('author accepted manuscript' – AAM) or the published version ('version of record' – VoR) of a publication to be made openly accessible in a repository.

NWO and ZonMw policy requires immediate OA (no embargo) supported by [the Rights Retention policy](#) as formulated by cOAlition S.

We see considerable variation in embargo terms as is shown in figure 6 and figure 7. The majority of Green OA papers have a maximum embargo period of 6 months. These are most likely articles that make use of the Article 25fa in the Dutch Copyright Law (Taverne-amendment), which allows researchers to make short scientific works publicly available through their institutional repository after 6 months. However, NWO and ZonMW do not accept embargo periods. Therefore, this remains an area to be worked on in cooperation with the institutions.

According to Unpaywall data, for 87,9% of the green OA publications funded by NWO or ZonMw and published in 2022, the published version (VoR) has been made available in a repository. 7,9% of the Green OA papers are either a 'submitted' version or AAM. For the remaining 4,2% of the papers we couldn't find any information about the version.

We must note that these statistics need to be interpreted with caution, since Unpaywall may not always be able to accurately distinguish between the submitted, accepted, and published version of a publication. And in some cases we have found that Unpaywall finds, and prioritises, the published version in a repository, even if it's published in a full OA journal.

Figure 6. Distribution of the different embargo periods for NWO publications (N=1100).

Figure 7. Distribution of the different embargo periods for ZonMw publications (N=157).

3.5 Estimating Plan S compliance

At least 64% of the included NWO and ZonMw publications from 2022 (3.688 out of 5.763) have been published via Gold, Hybrid, under a transformative agreement, or Green OA, with a CC-BY licence and is therefore fully Plan S compliant.

It remains a challenge to properly determine Plan S compliance for all publications. Not least because there is a transition phase between the old policy and the Plan S guidelines both for NWO and ZonMw. And as stated before, it is currently almost impossible to sort which articles were based on research proposals granted after the Plan S conditions became mandatory in 2021. Nevertheless, based on the figures presented in this report, we can certainly say that the majority of articles is published through eligible routes. In the coming years, when monitoring for OA routes becomes more sophisticated and detailed, and more articles are published following the Plan S requirements, we expect to see an increase of this percentage.

4 Conclusions

The percentage of OA has increased to 93% for the publication year 2022 (from 85% in 2020 and 90% in 2021). However, caution is needed when comparing this report's outcome with percentages from the CWTS-analyses, as the method of obtaining the data was different as described in the limitations section. Nonetheless it is evident that we are making significant steps in advancing OA.

NWO and ZonMw remain committed to ensuring that all publications that are the result of their funding programmes are made available OA. It is recommended that the attention in the coming years shifts away from focusing solely on 100% to including other aspects related to OA publishing. It will be important to also look at quality aspects of OA, like open licensing, abolishing embargo periods and implementing more inclusive and transparent business models (raising awareness and support for Diamond OA)⁷. This also relates to the Plan S compliance, which will gain significant importance in the coming years because there will be a growing number of publications stemming from projects that received funding from 2021 onward.

Furthermore, it is essential to identify mechanisms to ensure that researchers apply (correct) open licences when publishing their work and properly acknowledge their funding sources. It is also essential to make sure that metadata are open and of a better quality so that policy compliance assessment can be streamlined. NWO and ZonMw are committed to work on these topics with the different stakeholders involved to find better solutions that will smoothen the publishing processes.

⁷ Bosman, J., de Jonge, H., Kramer, B. and Sondervan, J., (2021). Advancing open access in the Netherlands after 2020: from quantity to quality. *Insights: the UKSG journal*, 34(1), p.16. [DOI](#).

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